

Final PhD Thesis Report

HME-AMR

**Investigating the role of heavy metals
in the environment as a selective
pressure for the dissemination of
antimicrobial resistance.**

Responsible OHEJP Partner: Teagasc
Contributing OHEJP partners: National
University of Ireland Galway, Veterinary
Institute of Norway

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	69 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

PhD Report	Final PhD Thesis Report Y5 (2022)
PhD Reference	R0566_ohelj
PhD candidate	Elena Anedda
PhD Lead Supervisor	Dr Kaye Burgess (Teagasc)
PhD second supervisor	Prof. Dearbháile Morris (University of Galway)
Other supervisor (s)	Dr Gro Johannessen (Norwegian Veterinary Institute)
Due month of the deliverable	M70
Actual submission month	MXX
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. This report will be entirely copied into One Health EJP Work Package 6 Deliverable D6.18 - Thesis Reports of up to 17 PhD studentships.</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> WOAH <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

INTRODUCTION

The final thesis or thesis report will be included in Deliverable 6.18 and the deadline to submit this deliverable to the European Commission is 30th June 2023. The deliverable will be a **public report** by default. **Where the final thesis report or final thesis contains information that must remain confidential under an embargoed period until the publications or outputs have been generated**, then a redacted version suitable for the public must be submitted.

A confidentiality clause should be included at the start of the redacted report or thesis clearly explaining any redactions, so the reader is aware. The embargo period should also be clearly stated.

- **PhDs that finish by 30th April 2023** are required to produce a drafted or final thesis as a final output. Once the PhD thesis is complete, PhD students should either submit an electronic version (PDF) of the thesis, or a DOI so that it can easily be linked (most theses are kept in a repository with open access unless by exception). The final thesis must be submitted to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) and uploaded to Zenodo by the PhD supervisor. In addition, the content covered in sections 1, 2, 7-16 of the thesis reporting template must also be completed and submitted to WP6 with the thesis and uploaded to Zenodo. Please ensure you upload the files in one Zenodo upload, so they have the same link.
- **PhD students that have not finished their PhD thesis by 30th April 2023** are required to produce a **Final Thesis Report** by completing the final thesis reporting template and to send a first version of the report back to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) **by 15th May 2023**.
- **In all cases**, PhD supervisors must submit the final (public) pdf(s) of the final PhD thesis to the WP6 team (wp6.onehealthjep@surrey.ac.uk) and **upload them to Zenodo by 30th June 2024**.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Where the final thesis report or final thesis contains information that must remain confidential under an embargoed period, then a redacted version suitable for the public must be submitted. The non-redacted final thesis (or a link to this document) must be emailed to the WP6 team when it is available.

A confidentiality clause should be included at the start of the report or thesis clearly explaining any redactions, so the reader is aware. The embargo period should also be clearly stated.

1. PhD Project team composition

PhD student: Elena Anedda

University at which the PhD is registered: University of Galway, Ireland.

Lead PhD Supervisor: Dr Kaye Burgess, Teagasc Food Research Centre, Ireland.

Second Supervisor: Prof. Dearbháile Morris, University of Galway, Ireland.

Other Supervisors: Dr Gro Johannessen, Norwegian Veterinary Institute, Norway.

Date for PhD thesis submission: 30/06/2024

The project started on the 1st of February 2021 after inevitable delays due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, the project is ongoing and it is anticipated that the thesis will be ready for submission by June 2024.

2. Abstract

500 words, 1 page. Please summarise the main scientific results and pay particular attention to the impact the project may have for the One Health EJP and its stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), and national ministries. This abstract may be used as a standalone communication piece, and therefore should be clear so it can be read as a separate entity if needed.

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the greatest threats to human and animal health. The concern of AMR has grown dramatically as a result of the overuse and misuse of antimicrobials in human and animal medicine, and agriculture. However, AMR emergence and dissemination is not only influenced by antimicrobial use. Other factors such as heavy metals and biocides, can have an impact on AMR spread. The *HME-AMR* project aims to investigate the role of heavy metals as a selective pressure on AMR in the primary food production environment. A scoping literature review was initially conducted to identify the knowledge gaps in the existing literature to summarise the evidence regarding the impact of heavy metals on AMR in the primary food production environment. The results obtained show a clear link between heavy metals and AMR in this sector. Specifically, the review reported that heavy metals can influence the abundance and spread of mobile genetic elements (MGEs), which can consequently facilitate the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). It also demonstrated that a wide variety of methods are used to assess relationships between AMR and heavy metals. A recommendation arising from the review is that harmonised approaches are needed to facilitate comparisons between different studies. Moreover, a limitation in the geographical distribution of the studies was observed; therefore, further research on AMR and heavy metals in the primary food production environment is needed to provide a more complete picture. In an effort to address this the role of heavy metals on AMR distribution in the primary food production environment was examined through a number of field based studies. The first study focused on the isolation and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales from soil and spinach samples collected from areas with zinc amendments and without. The second study also focused on the detection and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales in soil and bovine milk filters collected from production areas with high and low zinc concentrations across Ireland. The results of both studies demonstrate that primary food production environments can harbour clinically relevant antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales. These studies will be complemented by metagenomic analysis of selected sample sets to provide a further analysis of the resistome structure in areas of high and low zinc concentration. Although the studies are being conducted in Ireland, the results are broadly applicable and relevant to all the European countries. Findings of this work will contribute to meeting the objectives of *Ireland's Second National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance*, providing antimicrobial resistance in the food production environment and will be of relevance to the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System, considering that Ireland is a member of the EU AMR One Health Network.

3. Introduction and Objectives

Please provide a detailed introduction which includes a literature review, followed by an explanation of the project objectives, and the realised or expected outcomes, impact and cross-sector collaborations.

- *Expected outcomes:*
 - *Have the results been implemented in your institute, consortium partners, elsewhere? Across sectors? Are such implementations planned? Has this been discussed at the level of One Health EJP partner organisations? What should be done to do so?*
- *Expected impact:*
 - *Scientific impact: Can new research be based on the outputs?*
 - *Societal and policy impact: If implemented at different institutes or organisations, what would that mean for animal health, public health, food safety, for preparedness at national and international levels. Can the results be useful for EU reference laboratories, international organisations, One Health EJP stakeholders etc.*

Introduction:

Heavy metals are naturally occurring environmental compounds, which can influence antimicrobial resistance (AMR) dissemination. However, there is limited information on how heavy metals may act as a selective pressure on AMR in the primary food production environment. As part of *HME-AMR* a scoping literature review was conducted to summarise the evidence regarding the impact of heavy metals on AMR dissemination in the primary food production environment. A total of 73 studies, which met pre-established criteria, were included. These investigations were undertaken between 2008 and 2021, with a significant increase in the last three years. The majority of studies included were undertaken in China. Soil, water and manure were the most common samples analysed, and the sampling locations varied from areas with a natural presence of heavy metals, areas intentionally amended with heavy metals or manure, to areas close to industrial activity or mines. Fifty-four percent of the investigations focused on the analysis of four or more heavy metals, and copper and zinc were the metals most frequently analysed (n = 59, n = 49, respectively). The findings of this review highlight a link between heavy metals and AMR in the primary food production environment. Heavy metals impacted the abundance and dissemination of mobile genetic elements (MGEs) and antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs), with MGEs also observed as playing a key role in the spread of ARGs and metal resistance genes (MRGs). Harmonization of methodologies used in future studies would increase the opportunity for comparison between studies. Further research is also required to broaden the availability of data at a global level.

More details about the literature review can be found at

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121035>

Project Objectives:

Considering the significant impact of heavy metals on AMR, this project aims to investigate the presence of antimicrobial resistant bacteria and assess the bacterial resistomes in heavy metal-containing environments used for food production. In particular, the project focuses on the impact of zinc on antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales occurrence and composition in the primary food production environment. Zinc is a natural element present in the earth's crust; however, it is also commonly used in agriculture practices. For example, zinc is used to improve plant growth, as antifungal compound and for the prevention of livestock diseases. Enterobacterales are naturally present in the environment. However, antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales represent an important public health concern, particularly, Enterobacterales which are resistant to third generation cephalosporins and carbapenems, antimicrobials considered critically important by the World Health Organization. Therefore, the objectives of this project were: (1) analyse the antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales and resistome in soil and the associated crop, with and without zinc amendment; (2) compare the antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales and resistome in low and high zinc containing

soil and in bovine milk filters from cattle grazing on grass in these areas across Ireland; (3) compare isolates across One health domains.

Work is ongoing and it is expected to be completed by June 2024. It is anticipated that findings will impact on our understanding of the role of heavy metals in the emergence and dissemination of AMR in the primary food production environment.

Findings will inform national and international policy areas including but not limited to: Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC); EC (Drinking Water) Regulations 2014 (S.I. 122 of 2014); Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (85/337/EEC); Plant Protection Products Directive (91/414/EEC); Foodwise 2025, Foodvision 2030, National Farmed Animal Biosecurity Strategy 2021-2024, Working together for Animal Welfare: Ireland's Animal Welfare Strategy 2021-2025. It will also contribute to achieving the objectives of *Ireland's Second National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance*.

4. Materials and Methods

Option 1: Please provide details of the materials and methods used in as much detail as possible (consider this is a public report).

Option 2: If your materials and methods are part of a published scientific paper, please provide the DOI link to the scientific papers here instead.

The project started with a scoping literature review regarding the impact of heavy metals on AMR in the primary food production environment. The study of the existing literature was initiated in March 2021. After a discussion with members of the review panel, the following research question was formulated: "Do heavy metals have an impact on AMR in the primary food production environment?" Based on this question, combined search terms related to 'heavy metals', 'AMR', 'dissemination' and 'primary food production environment' were selected to define the search string. The search string was utilised in 5 different databases: Scopus, Embase, Medline, PubMed and Biosis (Web of Science). A total of 2868 articles were found and 1324 duplicates were removed. After the definition of inclusion and exclusion criteria, 1388 studies were excluded following title and abstract screening, while a further 82 articles were excluded following full text reading. Finally, 73 investigations were considered as most relevant to address the research question.

At the same time as the review was being drafted, two main field based studies were instigated. The first study (Chapter 2) focused on the isolation and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales from soil and spinach samples from zinc amended and control unamended plots. A total of 160 samples were collected in 2021 from two geographically distinct locations, where some plots were treated with zinc sulphate and others were used as control plots. The second study (Chapter 3) focused on the isolation and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales from soil and bovine milk filters from low and high zinc containing soils around Ireland. Fifty soil samples and 12 milk filters were collected in 2022 and 2023 from farms located in low and high zinc level areas across Ireland. The identification of suitable regions and recruitment of appropriate farms was facilitated through collaboration with GSI (Geological Survey Ireland) and the Teagasc Advisory Service. A second sampling of milk filters will take place at the end of May 2023.

Both studies (Chapters 2 and 3) employed a culture based approach. Samples were cultured on selective agars, specifically brilliance ESBL, msuperCARBA and MacConkey agar with a ciprofloxacin disc, for the detection of ESBL producing, carbapenemase resistant, and ciprofloxacin resistant bacteria, respectively. Blue and green colonies were selected from brilliance ESBL agar, red/pink and metallic blue colonies from msuperCARBA, and pink/red colonies from inside the halo around the ciprofloxacin disc on MacConkey. These isolates were then identified by MALDI-TOF, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing was completed in accordance with EUCAST and CLSI criteria. Selected isolates were subjected to whole genome sequencing and the results were analysed to identify antimicrobial

resistance genes, metal resistance genes and plasmids using Resfinder, CARD, Megares and Plasmidfinder databases. The samples collected from both studies were also stored at - 80°C for metagenomic analysis, the main objective of Chapter 4 which is ongoing.

5. Scientific Results and Discussion

Please provide your scientific results and discussion in this section and organise them into chapters (see below) which follow a clear 'storyline'. Describe all other aspects which contributed to the findings (e.g., integrative activities, collaborations etc.).

Please provide as much detail as possible (consider this is a public report) and include enough detail to understand the work done and outcomes (e.g. milestones, deliverables, outputs) of all Work Packages (e.g. WP1, WPN) and associated tasks (e.g. WP1 – T1, WPN – TN...).

a. Chapter 1: Evaluating the impact of heavy metals on antimicrobial resistance in the primary food production environment: A scoping review

The literature review shows a rapid increase in the number of relevant studies since 2016 regarding the role of the environment in the development and transmission of AMR. The studies included in the scoping review considered different types of environmental samples: soil, water and manure principally; but also examined the characteristics of the environment where they were collected from, for example the vicinity to mines or industries, or exposure to a specific treatment. Through the analysis of the included studies, an association between AMR and the presence of heavy metals was generally observed. In some cases, a direct correlation was established, such as promotion of ARGs dissemination induced by heavy metals; while in other cases, the role of MGEs on the spread of ARGs and MRGs was demonstrated. Specifically, a limitation in the geographical representativeness of studies included, heterogeneity of methods applied to detect AMR and HMR, and the effect of heavy metals on MGEs, were discussed in the review. Full details can be found in the published study

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121035>

b. Chapter 2: Occurrence and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales in soil and spinach in the presence and absence of zinc amendment

The work undertaken for this chapter has been drafted for submission for publication. To ensure this publication process is not compromised detailed results have not been included, with a brief synopsis provided of the results instead.

A number of Enterobacterales isolates representing five different species were obtained from both the soil and spinach samples in both locations tested, including multi drug resistant isolates. Whole genome sequencing (WGS) analysis of the isolates complemented the phenotypic analysis, facilitating genotypic confirmation of the antimicrobial resistance phenotypes observed.

c. Chapter 3: Occurrence and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales in dairy production environments of differing zinc concentrations

This work is still in progress and due for completion by September 2023. To ensure the publication process is not compromised, detailed results to date are not included.

This work is ongoing but to date antimicrobial resistant isolates of seven different Enterobacterales species have been identified from both soil and milk filter samples, with a diverse range of AMR profiles

characterised. Analysis is ongoing to compare the phenotypic and genotypic profiles of the isolates via antimicrobial susceptibility testing and WGS. They will also be compared with relevant isolates from other One Health domains, through the interrogation of public databases and collaboration with other OHEJP project partners, including those involved in ARDiG and DiSCoVeR.

d. Chapter 4: Metagenomic analysis of soil and bovine milk filters

This work is still in progress and due for completion by January 2024. As this work is not scheduled for completion until early 2024 further details cannot be provided at this time.

The previous two chapters focus on a group of antimicrobial resistant organisms of particular public health concern. However, in order to gain a more complete understanding of the differences which may exist in AMR profiles in association with heavy metal content it is important to look at the wider microbial community, including unculturable species. To facilitate this DNA has been extracted from a subset of samples collected as part of Chapter 3 and these are currently undergoing metagenomic analysis. Analysis will predominantly focus on the characterisation of the resistome through the detection of ARGs, as well as MGEs and heavy metal and biocide resistance genes.

6. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

500 words, 1 page (Calibri or Arial Font size 11, margins of minimum 2cm). Please provide conclusions based on the work achieved, and any future recommended work.

Based on the work completed to date it is clear that a better understanding of how heavy metals can influence AMR and ARGs in the primary food production environment is needed to inform the development of effective mitigation measures. Limited investigations regarding heavy metals and AMR dissemination in the environment have been conducted to date in many regions of the world. Therefore, more research is needed to better understand the mechanisms through which heavy metals impact on AMR, particularly in the context of feed and food production. Harmonising the approaches to AMR and HMR analysis and measurement of heavy metal concentration is critical. The field-based studies undertaken as part of HME-AMR help address this knowledge gap and, although not yet fully complete, have demonstrated the presence of a diverse range of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacteriales in the primary production environment, providing a potential route into the food chain. Investigation of potential linkages with heavy metal resistance are currently ongoing. Characterisation of these isolates and comparison with those derived from other One Health domains will help further elucidate the role of primary production in the transmission of AMR and the factors which influence it.

Metagenomic analysis provides the opportunity to obtain more indepth information on AMR profiles in microbial communities using a culture independent approach. It will be utilised to examine the resistome in areas of high and low zinc concentrations to determine associations which may exist. Such information will address identified knowledge gaps and inform production practices in the future to mitigate the dissemination of AMR.

7. PhD project self-evaluation

500 words, 1 page (Calibri or Arial Font size 11, margins of minimum 2cm). Please comment to what extent the initial PhD project objectives as laid out in the proposal have been met. Any deviation from the original project proposal should be included and justified.

As outlined above the project objectives indicated in the proposal have been achieved through a number of research based chapters which are complete, or well on their way to completion. All necessary sampling plans were prepared through collaboration with Geological Survey Ireland and the Teagasc advisory service, broadening the awareness of the project and its objectives. All necessary

samples have been collected and the isolation and characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacteriales in low and high metal containing environments, as well as in bovine milk filters from cattle grazing on grass in low and high metal areas, have been completed. Complementary metagenomics analysis which will form the content of Chapter 4 is currently under way. Together these chapters will provide an overview of the presence of antimicrobial resistant organisms and ARGs of public health concern in the production of both plant and animal derived products and whether the presence or addition of zinc may influence the AMR patterns observed.

There was one necessary deviation from the project proposal. From 2022, high level zinc oxide supplementation in pig diets is no longer permitted in the EU, which impacted on one *HME-AMR* objective. Specifically, one objective in the original proposal was the analysis of the resistome on sites following manure application from pigs with heavy metal included in feed and from pigs with no/minimal heavy metal in feed. However, with the removal of the use of high levels of ZnO in pig production there was an associated expected decrease in Zn levels in slurry being land spread and also greater difficulty in identifying farms to fulfil the requirements for meeting the project objective. This study was therefore replaced with the spinach focused study. The revised study objective was to assess the AMR profile in spinach and soil in the presence and absence of zinc amendment. In this case zinc sulphate was directly applied to the soil, with unamended control plots also available. This enabled direct comparison of the impact of zinc amendment on the AMR profile. This project amendment has been reported and approved previously.

As part of completing this PhD a range of microbiological and molecular skills have been learnt by the student, as well as bioinformatics analysis. They have also had the opportunity to improve their presentation and communication skills, in both oral and written formats, which led to being awarded a 'best oral presentation' prize at the recent ENVIRON conference.

8. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

The following list refers to the deliverables and milestones as mentioned in the successive project Annual Work Plans. This part of the report should demonstrate that the project has delivered all that was planned.

Please verify, correct if required, complete, and ensure that all deliverables are uploaded - both on the private project group of the One Health EJP website and on Zenodo.

Note that all deliverables should be public by default. If a deliverable should be temporarily confidential, the justification should be mentioned in the Document Management section in the deliverable template, and the Deliverable Confidentiality Statement Form should be completed and submitted, which provide details of when the deliverable can be made public. It is the responsibility of the PhD supervisor to keep the WP6 team informed of any delays to making these deliverables public. In exceptional circumstances where confidentiality is required indefinitely, this should be clearly justified.

If applicable, please assign an integrative category (1 to 8) to each of the deliverables, as this helps PMT to assess possible impacts the outcome may have.

Deliverables

Please fill the table belows. If a delay is due to the COVID-19 crisis, please add a comment. if there are no corrections required then no action is necessary.

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.1	Report on AMR bacteria present in soils of differing heavy metal content	M60	M72	Delay in student starting project due to COVID-19 and rearrangement of study commencement order will delay the first deliverable being achieved.	1.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.2	Report on the impact of the application of heavy metal containing amendments to AMR bacteria in soil	M54	M69	The study has been completed and is currently being written up for publication.	5.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.3	Report on AMR bacteria present in milk filters from animals grazing in areas of differing heavy metal content	M66	M72	Delay in student starting project due to COVID-19 will delay the achievement of this deliverable.	5.

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
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PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	1	SOP in place for sampling culture based analysis	M27	M40	Yes	Delayed due to the late recruitment of student but the SOPs for culture based analysis are now in place and have been utilised in the first sampling study undertaken.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	2	Sequences of sufficient quality obtained from metagenomic analysis	M35	M68	No	Delayed due to late recruitment of PhD student but data will be available by M69.

9. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

Please describe any link (workshops, meetings, missions etc.) with a Joint Research Project or Joint Integrative Project.

- A number of meetings took with Geological Survey Ireland and through collaboration with the Tellus survey (<https://www.gsi.ie/en-ie/programmes-and-projects/tellus/Pages/default.aspx>). This enabled the selection of suitable high and low metal content areas across Ireland for resistome analysis in soil and bovine milk filters (Chapter 3) and also increased awareness of the project in other sectors.
- Dr Burgess and Prof Morris both contribute to Ireland's Second National Action Plan for Antimicrobial Resistance and the results of this project will contribute to achieving the objectives of that plan.
- Dr Burgess and Dr Johannessen were both participants of the OHEJP DISCoVeR project which focused on source attribution of a range of pathogens and AMR E. coli. Isolates from this study will be of relevance for the One Health strain database built as part of the DISCoVeR project and the linkages forged through the DISCoVeR project will enable access for the student to suitable strain data for comparative purposes.

10. -Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

Please describe any link with any external (EU, national and international) relevant project (name + website), or with the One Health EJP [stakeholders](#).

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As part of the study described in Chapter 2, we collaborated with a DAFM funded project which is focused on the impact of different soil amendments on cadmium uptake in food crops. We focused on plots where zinc has been applied and use the corresponding control (no amendment) plots for comparison.

- This project is complementary to the EPA funded *AREST* project (<https://www.nuigalway.ie/medicine-nursing-and-health-sciences/medicine/disciplines/bacteriology/research/arest/>) which is examining antimicrobial resistance in the environment. Prof Morris is the coordinator of this project and Dr Burgess is a participant. The culture based methodologies being employed in *AREST* were particularly relevant for *HME-AMR*. We collaborated on an ongoing basis with these colleagues for methodologies and isolate characterisation.

- *HME-AMR* is complementary to an ongoing PhD project (*ZnO*) in Dr Burgess' group focusing on the impact of zinc oxide supplementation on the porcine resistome which facilitated a smooth transition for the *HME-AMR* student in relation to methodologies and analysis.

- *HME-AMR* is complementary to a project led by Dr Orla O'Sullivan as part of the SFI funded *VistaMilk* project (<https://vistamilk.ie/>) which is examining the soil resistome in different sites across Ireland. Dr Burgess and Dr O'Sullivan will collaborate to ensure synergy of the projects and avoid duplication and the PhD students on both projects have collaborated on methodology to ensure harmonisation of their approaches

11. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

Please describe here what you perceived as additional value as a result of your PhD being a part of the One Health EJP e.g. training, networking with other disciplines or countries and access to a wide range of expertise.

Being part of the One Health EJP has given the student the opportunity to create a wide network with colleagues who work on different topics, but whom share the same One Health principles. Attending conferences, including OHEJP ASM 2021 and OHEJP ASM 2022, enabled the sharing of ideas among participants, which helped the student to evaluate and see their own work from a different point of view, bringing innovation and motivation. Also, being part of the OHEJP community on social media, such as LinkedIn, led the student has interacted with multiple people and was informed about the latest news. Moreover, training, such as the ASM Satellite Workshops, broadened her general knowledge.

12. Transferrable skills and Training

Describe details of relevant transferrable skills, training courses or CPD training attended and undertaken by the PhD student throughout the PhD programme.

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Biosafety Awareness	Health and Safety	23/04/21	Teagasc
Lab risk assessment	Health and Safety	29/04/21	Teagasc
Lab chemical safety awareness	Health and Safety	19/04/21	Teagasc
Lab safety basics	Health and Safety	17/03/21	Teagasc
Manual handling	Health and Safety	08/02/21	Teagasc
Antimicrobial resistance –theory and methods	Relevant to PhD topic	04/02/21	Coursera
Metagenomics applied to surveillance of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance	Relevant to PhD topic	19/02/21	Coursera
Scopus workshop	Database interrogation	24/03/21	University of Galway
Present your research with confidence	Presentation skills	24/05/21	Environ 2021
Statistical analysis with R	Statistics	14-17-18/06/21	Teagasc
The Impostor Syndrome	Mental Health	06/07/21	Walsh Scholarships Programme
Health and Safety Briefings	Health and Safety	26/08/21	University of Galway

Academic Writing Centre summer workshop	Writing skills	27/08/21	University of Galway
<i>Understanding AMR in Water-Webinar</i>	Relevant to PhD topic	28/08/21	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
General Data Protection Regulation	Data protection online	30/08/21	Teagasc (E-Learning)
Safety Responsibilities for Principal Investigators	Laboratory Safety	30/08/21	University of Galway
Safety Responsibilities for Heads of Units	Laboratory Safety	31/08/21	University of Galway
Chemical safety training	Laboratory Safety	31/08/21	University of Galway
Academic English Writing	Writing skills	21/09 - 23/11 (10 lessons)	University of Galway -English Language Centre
Plain English Training	Writing skills	27/09/21	Teagasc-NALA
Mental Health Workshop	Mental Health	28/09/21	Spectrum Life
Gas Cylinders	Health and Safety	15/10/21	Teagasc
AMR Surveillance in The Netherlands (and beyond) from a One Health perspective	Relevant to PhD topic	18/10/21	MetVetNet Association
One Health Annual Conference	Relevant to PhD topic	03-04/10/21	Ryan Institute Centre
Online writing workshop	Writing skills	01/12/21	University of Galway -Academic Writing Centre
CMNHS English Language Workshop	Writing skills	Feb-Mar-Apr (30 hours)	University of Galway -English Language Centre
Research Integrity	Training to conduct research	April 2022	Epigeum
Bioinformatic Workshop	Data analysis	20/05/2022 27/05/2022 13/06/2022	Teagasc
JPIAMR Workshop-New perspectives on bacterial drug resistance	Antimicrobial resistance	09/06/2022	JPIAMR
UCD One Health Conference 2022	One Health	15/06/2022	UCD
ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference 2022	Antimicrobial resistance	21-24/06/2022	EFSA
VIBE-Conference	Bioinformatic	24/06/2022	University of Limerick
DGSA-Training	Shipment of research specimens	07/07/2022	Teagasc
The Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and Alternatives to Antibiotics (ATA) Research Webinar Series	Antimicrobial resistance	14/06/2022 19/07/2022 20/09/2022	U.S Department of Agriculture

		18/10/2022	
Antimicrobial Resistance and Use in the Farming Sector: Negotiating Behaviour Change under New Legislations-Seminar	Antimicrobial resistance	28/09/2022	Safefood & Teagasc
ESCMID/ASM Conference on Drug Development to Meet the Challenge of Antimicrobial Resistance	Antimicrobial resistance	04-07/10/2022	European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID)
Centre for One Health Annual Conference 2022	One Health and Antimicrobial resistance	03-04/11/2022	Ryan Institute
Teagasc Festival of Farming and Food (Science Week)	Oral presentation skill	15/11/2022	Teagasc
BTYSTE-BT Young Scientist & Technology Exhibition	Oral presentation skill	12/01/2023	BTYSTE
Environmental DNA sequencing with Oxford Nanopore: in the lab and in the field	Relevant to PhD topic	26/01/2023	Oxford Nanopore Technologies
Lab Chemical Safety Awareness	Health and Safety	8/03/2023	Teagasc
Chemical Spill Awareness Training	Health and Safety	22/03/2023	Teagasc
ASM training (Next Generation sequencing)	Relevant to PhD topic	March/April/June 2023	American Society for Microbiology

13. Ethical Reviews

Please fill the table below. If there are no corrections required, then no action is necessary.

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020

14. Scientific Publications

Please fill the table below.

Please make sure that all publications are listed. List peer-reviewed publications and others.

For every publication please specify:

- Doi reference

- Zenodo **link**
- Gold or green open access?
 - o *If green: Length of the Embargo, if any. Open access to the publication must be ensured within a maximum of six months.*

If no doi reference (e.g. article in journal, publication in conference proceedings or workshop, book or monograph, chapter in a book, thesis/dissertation, other), please provide as much information as possible.

Publication date	Publication title	Authors	DOI reference	Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? *please specify embargo length	Is it a Gold Open Access?
06/01/2023	Evaluating the impact of heavy metals on antimicrobial resistance in the primary food production environment: A scoping review	Anedda, Elena; Farrell, Maeve Louise; Morris, Dearbháile; Burgess, Catherine M.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121035	https://zenodo.org/record/7565730#.ZE6y8nbMI2w	Yes	Yes, 24 months	No

15. Additional Outputs

Other relevant dissemination outcomes can be highlighted here, e.g. non-scientific publications, proceedings, poster, video, tools, guidelines, patents, etc. If the outcome is a deliverable it should not be mentioned here.

Please indicate where the item can be found, for instance on Zenodo or any open access repository. Please indicate the link and check the functionality.

- Anedda, E., Burgess, C., Morris, D. (2021). A scoping review to evaluate the impact of heavy metals in the agri-food environment as selective pressure for the mobilisation of antimicrobial resistance. Poster presentation. ONE HEALTH EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Copenhagen, Denmark, 09-11 June 2021.
- Anedda, E.; Madigan, G.; Morris, D.; Burgess, C. (2022). Assessment of the presence of antimicrobial resistant bacteria in spinach and its production environment after zinc application. Poster presentation. ONE HEALTH EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, Italy, 11-13 April 2022.
- Anedda, E.; Madigan, G.; Morris, D.; Burgess, C. (2022). Evaluating the impact of zinc application on the presence of antimicrobial resistance in spinach and its production environment. Poster presentation. ONE Conference 2022, Brussels, Belgium, 21-24 June 2022.
- Anedda, E., Ekhlās, D., Alexa, E., Gaffney, M., Madigan, G., Morris, D.1, Burgess, C.M. (2023). Occurrence of AMR Enterobacterales in soil and spinach in the presence and absence of zinc amendment. Oral presentation. Environ Conference 2023, Donegal, Ireland, 3-5 April 2023.
- Anedda, E.; Madigan, G.; Croffie, M.; Morris, D.; Burgess, C. (2023). Assessment of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales from the dairy production environment in low and high zinc containing areas. Poster presentation. ARAE Conference 2023, Tours, France, 3-5 July 2023.

16. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

In this paragraph you have the possibility to draw the attention to remarkable achievements that could be highlighted to illustrate the potential impact of your project.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

The project is still in progress with an anticipated end date of June 2024. Details on specific outcomes to be highlighted will be included upon project completion. It is expected that the project outputs which will be published, describing isolates and AMR profiles in a range of ecological niches, will be of direct interest to a range of stakeholders, including policymakers, regulators, veterinarians, farmers, clinicians and the research community amongst others.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Some of the outcomes of the project may already be in use or planned to be implemented in one or more partner institutes, or in external organisation (including stakeholders' organisations), or at the level of national authorities. Please describe.

This will be more applicable following completion of the project in mid 2024.

17. One Health impact

About 500 words, 1 page – *This part is extremely important, also for the One Health EJP stakeholders. Please, describe the impact of the PhD project, reflecting at least the following aspects:*

- *Specify any direct or indirect impact the outcome of your project may have for international stakeholders active in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and/or emerging threats (ECDC, EFSA, FAO, WOA/WHO-EU; EU reference laboratories, etc.) e.g. suggested improvements of existing /planned surveillance programmes, new relevant databases for risk assessment updates, improved methodologies for risk assessment and management, etc.*
- *Please describe how regional or national authorities and stakeholders may implement and/or integrate any of the results from the project in their work. Which contacts, if any, have been taken between your consortium and authorities or stakeholders that may lead to such a knowledge transfer? Please describe.*
- *Has this project helped you building and strengthening the networking with other partners of the One Health EJP and beyond? Please describe shortly and give some examples.*

Although the project was conducted in Ireland, the results are broadly applicable and relevant to all the European countries. The provided data on AMR will contribute to meeting the objectives of Ireland's Second National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance and to the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System, considering that Ireland is a member of the EU AMR One Health Network. As identified in the scoping literature review there are limited studies on heavy metal and AMR linkages in food production, particularly in Europe, and the outcomes of this project will help address that gap. Such data will inform more targeted risk management of AMR in food production.

The project team are members of a national One Health AMR Thematic Network which will provide an ideal forum for sharing project outcomes with a diverse range of stakeholders and its activities have also been reported through the national OHEJP mirror group.

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris collaborated on the Irish EPA funded project AREST which examined antimicrobial resistance in the environment and contributed to One Health orientated AMR research and policy making at a national and international level. This project is highly complementary to those activities and will facilitate an increasing collaborative relationship between the research groups. Dr Burgess has worked previously with Dr Johannessen of the Norwegian Veterinary Institute as part of the *HUPLANT Control* COST action focusing on microbial food safety issues and this project will further develop this relationship. This project has also led to Dr Burgess forging collaborative linkages with Geological Survey Ireland in relation to heavy metal mapping and with the SFI funded *VISTA MILK* research centre. This work has contributed to Dr Burgess and Prof Morris submitting an application for national research funding on AMR mitigation measures in the environment which has recently been funded.

Ms Anedda has actively participated in OHEJP conference and training activities and has had the opportunity to share and discuss her work with colleagues in different disciplines and One Health domains, ensuring that the role of food production in AMR transmission is more fully understood, as well as the factors which may influence it. Once complete, the work of *HME-AMR* will provide complementary culture dependent and independent analysis of antimicrobial resistance of public health concern in horticultural crops and dairy production, as well as the environment in which they are produced. This will provide a valuable link between One Health domains.

18. List of dissemination and communication activities

Please fill in one table per event you attended/organised during the entire life span of the project. Please make sure they are registered online on the OneHealth EJP webpage:

<https://surveys.sciensano.be/index.php/754325?lang=en>

If relevant (for instance flyer, video, etc.) please include hyperlink.

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	June 9-11 2021		
Place:	Copenhagen/online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (poster)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	June 9-11 2021		
Place:	Copenhagen/online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (Thesis in 3 minutes)

<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes (poster)</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (Thesis in 3 minutes)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (Roundtable discussion talk)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	

Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ONE Conference 2022		
Date:	June 21-24 2022		
Place:	Brussels/online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (poster)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	IAFP European Symposium		
Date:	May 4-6 2022		
Place:	Munich, Germany		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (presentation)

<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	Environ 2023		
Date:	April 03-05 2023		
Place:	Letterkenny, Donegal, Ireland /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes (Oral presentation)</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	

<i>Policy Makers</i>			
Name of the activity:	ARAE 2023		
Date:	July 03-05 2023		
Place:	Tours, France /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes (Poster presentation)</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			